

FEMALE CHALLENGED PERSON'S HOROSCOPES - A STUDY

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Abstract:

Astrological reason for Challenged person in Female's horoscope with planetary position analysis is done.

Key Words: Challenged Person, Parts of Body, Kalapurush Rasi, Rule for, Differently Abled

Introduction:

Medical astrology is the very vital branch in Vedic astrology. The knowledge of the medical astrology is must for each and every astrologers. We can prevent diseases and also take precaution through the help of medical astrology. Here we should see the planetary positions of the male disabled challenged persons horoscopes.

Malefic Planets:

Sun, Mars, Saturn, Rahu and kethu are called malefic planets. They always do harm.

Benefic Planets: Jupiter, Venus, Mercury and sukla paksha Moon are called benefic planets. They always do good.

Malefic Bhavas:

Sixth, Eighth and twelveth bhavas are called malefic bhavas.

Sixth Bhava:

It plays a vital role in medical astrology. We can calculate the strength of the disease through this bhava.

Eighth Bhava:

It denotes how one will suffer. It indicates accidents and surgeries when it connects with the sixth bhava it would become very dangerous.

Twelveth Bhava:

It denotes hospitalization and removal of the organs.

Rasis and the Part of Kala Purush:

Rasi	Part of Kala Purush
Aries	Head
Taurus	Face
Gemini	Neck
Cancer	Chest and heart
Leo	Upper abdomen
Virgo	Lower abdomen
Libra	Waist
Scorpio	Genital organ
Sagittarius	Thigh
Capricorn	Knee
Aquaris	Carp
Pisces	Feet

Bhavas and the Parts of Kala Purush:

Bhava	Part of Kala purush
1	Head and brain
2	Face, eyes, nose, tongue, teeth, ears, fingers and nails.
3	Neck, throat and hands
4	Heart, lungs and chest
5	Upper abdomen and sub conscious mind
6	Lower abdomen, navel and bones
7	Waist and sperm
8	Genital and reproductive Organs (i.e) kidney

9	Thigh
10	Knee and knee joints
11	Carp
12	Feet

Fire Signs:

Aries, Leo and Sagittarius are called fire signs. They give stamina to the body.

Earth Signs:

Taurus, Virgo and Capricorn are called earth signs They governs bones and muscles in our body.

Air Signs:

Gemini, Libra and Aquaris are called air signs They governs breath (inhale and exhale)

Water Signs:

Cancer, Scorpio and Pisces are called water signs. It governs blood circulation in our body.

Planets and their Related Parts:

- Sun governs bones and bone marrow.
- Moon governs blood and blood vessels.
- Mars governs the body structure.
- Mercury governs skins and nerves.
- Jupiter governs muscles and tissues.
- Venus governs the growth of bones and sperms.
- Saturn indicates the weakness of bones.
- Rahu indicates the disfunction of the organ and the organ removal.
- Kethu indicates the critical situation of the organs.

Rules for Challenging Persons in Female According to Horoscope:

- Sixth, Eighth (or) Twelveth lord stands in Sagittarius.
- Rahu or Kethu or Saturn stands in Sixth or Eighth or Twelveth. bhava.
- Sun or Mars stands in sixth, eighth or twelveth bhava or the star of sixth, eighth, twelveth bhava's lord or the star of Saturn, Rahu and Kethu.
- Sixth, eighth or twelveth bhava lords stands in the stars of Sun, Mars, Saturn, Rahu or Kethu.
- Mars stands in Saturn stars or Saturn stands in Mars stars.
- Sixth lord stands in eighth or twelveth bhava in its own star.

Example 1:

Name : Sonu
 Date of Birth : 10.10.1988
 Time of birth : 12.10 am
 Place of birth : Gorakhpur (U.P)
 Moon dasa balance : 9 years 6 Months 30 Days

MARS (R)	10	JUPITER (R)	MANTHI	RAHU	JUPITER (R) MOON	SATURN	11
RAHU	RASI		ASC	7	NAVAMSA		VENUS SUN
7			KETHU VENUS	6			ASC MERCURY (R)
SATURN	5	4	MOON SUN MERCURY (R)	5	MANTHI	3	KETHU MARS (R)

Planet	Degree	Star	Padam	Rasi	Navamsa
Lagna	093.28	Pusam	1	Cancer	Leo
Sun	173.04	Hastha	4	Virgo	Cancer
Moon	160.38	Hastha	1	Virgo	Aries
Mars	338.28	Uthratathi	2	Pisces	Virgo
Mercury	176.20	Chitra	1	Virgo	Leo
Jupiter	042.07	Rohini	1	Taurus	Aries
Venus	132.27	Maga	4	Leo	Cancer
Saturn	243.37	Moolam	2	Sagittarius	Taurus
Rahu	318.34	Sathayam	4	Aquaris	Pisces

Kethu	138.34	Pooram	2	Leo	Virgo
Manthi	63.23	Mirgashira	4	Gemini	Scorpio

Moon dasa till age	9 years	6 months	30 Days
Mars dasa till age	16 years	6 months	30 Days
Rahu dasa till age	34 years	6 months	30 Days

Current Rahu dasa Mars bukti till 09 May 2023

She met a serve accident in Mars dasa Saturn bukthi. Her left hand and leg were severely damaged.

How Our Rules Give Result in this Horoscope?

Rule Number 1:

Sixth, Eighth (or) Twelveth lord stands in Sagittarius.

In this horoscope the eighth lord Saturn stands in Sagittarius.

Rule Number 2:

Rahu or Kethu or Saturn stands in Sixth or Eighth or Twelveth. bhava.

In this horoscope Rahu stands in eighth bhava

Rule Number 3:

Sun or Mars stands in sixth, eighth or twelveth bhava or the star of sixth, eighth, twelveth bhava's lord or the star of Saturn, Rahu and Kethu. In this horoscope Mars stands in eighthbhava lord's star. It is also the star of Saturn

Rule Number 4:

Sixth, eighth or twelveth bhava lords stands in the stars of Sun, Mars, Saturn, Rahu or Kethu.

In this horoscope twelveth lord Mercury stands in chitra, the star of Mars. Saturn the eighth lord stand is in moolam, the star of Kethu.

Rule Number 5:

Mars stands in Saturn stars or Saturn stands in Mars stars.

In this horoscope Mars stand in the star of saturn uthiratathi.

Totally five rules are applicable out of six.

Example 1:

Name : Bhuvana Sri
 Date of Birth : 23.12.1986
 Time of birth : 01.52 pm
 Place of birth : Madhyam gram (west Bengal)
 Janma Lagna : Aries
 Janma Rasi : Leo
 Janma Star : Pooram 4
 Saturn dasa balance : 1 years 11 Months 25 Days

RAHU	ASC	2	3
MANTHI	RASI		4
JUPITER	RASI		MOON
MARS	RASI		10
SUN	SATURN	VENUS	KETHU
	MERCURY		

MANTHI	VENUS	MARS	SUN
JUPITER	NAVAMSA		KETHU
MERCURY	NAVAMSA		12
RAHU	NAVAMSA		4
STURN	MOON	2	ASC

Planet	Degree	Star	Padam	Rasi	Navamsa
Lagna	019.59	Bharani	2	Aries	Virgo
Sun	247.37	Moolam	3	Sagittarius	Gemini
Moon	145.26	Pooram	4	Leo	Scorpio
Mars	325.07	Puratathi	2	Aquaris	Taurus
Mercury	236.13	Jyeshta	3	Scorpio	Aquaris
Jupiter	322.40	Puratathi	1	Aquaris	Aries
Venus	203.20	Visagam	1	Libra	Aries
Saturn	230.49	Jyeshta	2	Scorpio	Capricorn
Rahu	353.21	Revathi	2	Pisces	Capricorn
Kethu	173.21	Hastham	4	Virgo	Cancer
Manthi	358.56	Revathi	4	Pisces	Pisces

Current Period:

Rahu dasa Kethu bukthi

Both her legs disfunctioned at her earlier life.

Venus dasa till age	01 year	11 Months	25 Days
Sun dasa till age	07 years	11 Months	25 Days
Moon dasa till age	17 years	11 Months	25 Days
Mars dasa till age	24 years	11 Months	25 Days
Rahu dasa till age	42 years	11 Months	25 Days

How Our Rules Give Result in this Horoscope?

Rule Number 2:

Rahu or Kethu or Saturn stands in Sixth or Eighth or Twelveth. bhava.

In this horoscope Rahu stands in twelveth bhava, Kethu stands in sixth bhava and saturn stands in eighth bhava. Highly dangerous one.

Rule Number 3:

Sun or Mars stands in sixth, eighth or twelveth bhava or the star of sixth, eighth, twelveth bhava's lord or the star of Saturn, Rahu and Kethu.

In this horoscope Sun stands in Moolam, the star of Kethu and Mars stands with twelveth bhava lord's star puratathi.

Rule Number 6:

Sixth lord stands in eighth or twelveth bhava in its own star.

In this horoscope the sixth lord Mercury stands in eighth bhava in its own star jyeshta.

Totally three rules are applicable out of six

Conclusion:

We understand the reason for the born of challenged persons from the above examples. Karma is the most important factor. This type of born is due to our previous janma karma. We had done lot of evils to others in our past janma. So, God punished us in this janma. So, we can avail the opportunity in our day to day life, we must do so many good karmas to others like physical help or material help Thus we balance our karma.

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